

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Modelling icebergs, bathymetry and sea ice interactions

Deliverable D2.1

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Cover sheet: Icebergs grounded on Bear Ridge, Amundsen Sea (Sentinel-1 satellite image on 24-OCT-2023). The open ocean appears in black (Amundsen Polynya), while the sea-ice-covered area appears in grey. The contours are the isobaths (interval of 50 m). The frontal parts of Dotson and Crosson ice shelves are visible in the lower part of the image.

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History of Changes

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Version 1	2 February 2026	Submitted version	Anna Olivé Abelló,
Version 2	3 March 2026	Editing of the caption of Fig. 1	Chiara Bearzotti

1. Publishable summary

Icebergs play a key role in the climate system by distributing about half of the glacial freshwater released by Antarctica to the Southern Ocean. Some icebergs get grounded on shallow ridges and play the role of an anchor for sea ice, with thicker sea ice often fastened to them. Such fast ice favours the opening of coastal polynyas, where most Antarctic sea ice is produced. The climatic importance of icebergs has motivated the development of models treating icebergs as Lagrangian particles put in motion by forces exerted by the atmosphere, ocean and sea ice. In current models, however, these Lagrangian icebergs do not interact with bathymetry, i.e., they do not ground on shallow bathymetric ridges as observed. This limits our ability to project future sea-ice production rates and water mass transformation, including Antarctic Bottom Water formation.

Here we present the development of a new generation of Lagrangian iceberg model that is capable of interacting with bathymetry. First, this has required some work to better estimate the thickness of icebergs. Most previous studies used a thickness of 250 m for the largest iceberg classes, following the typical ice-shelf thickness suggested by a limited number of ship observations, and independently of the calving location. In the new model version, icebergs inherit the thickness of their calving ice shelf, and their keel depth often exceeds 400 m, making them more likely to ground on bathymetric ridges. The second part of our work has consisted of explicitly representing the dissipative forces at the iceberg base when they move over shallow bathymetry. This includes the representation of both the energy dissipation when icebergs penetrate into a sediment layer of a few meters thick, and the Coulomb friction against the solid bedrock if the iceberg penetrates all the way through the sediment layer. In the case of a contact with the solid bedrock, the iceberg kinetic energy is converted into potential energy and the iceberg is lifted above floatation.

From these developments, we show that a first effect of iceberg grounding is to keep the meltwater closer to Antarctica, and a second effect is to favour the formation of fast ice and polynya. Both significantly affect the vertical structure of the ocean around Antarctica. We were also able to propose a quantitative force balance for both freely floating and grounding icebergs. A three-force balance between wind stress, the ocean pressure gradient and the Coriolis force largely explain the motions of freely floating icebergs, with little net acceleration as all these forces are nearly perpendicular to motion. The interaction with the sediments changes this, icebergs being mostly pushed forward by the winds, with a strong deceleration due to sediment resistance. In cases where icebergs interact with the solid bedrock, they usually stop within a day.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Scientific context

Iceberg melting in the Southern Ocean affects sea ice formation both by cooling the ocean surface and by enhancing the ocean stratification, thereby reducing oceanic deep convection. Some model projections have suggested that a future increase in iceberg melt could delay atmospheric warming in the Southern Hemisphere and activate a positive feedback mechanism between surface freshening, subsurface warming and ice-sheet/shelf melting, which could accelerate ice mass loss around Antarctica. Currently, iceberg melting contributes approximately as much as ice shelf basal melting to the glacial freshwater from Antarctica into the Southern Ocean, but their melting patterns are very different. While the ice shelf meltwater is released close to Antarctica, icebergs travel long distances and can melt all over the Southern Ocean.

Most ocean and climate models have a very poor representation of glacial freshwater fluxes around Antarctica, but a few models have the capability of representing individual icebergs or groups of icebergs as Lagrangian particles. In this case, the calving flux is provided by satellite products or ice sheet models and distributed into several iceberg classes of predefined size and thickness. In current models, these Lagrangian icebergs do not interact with bathymetry, i.e., they do not ground on shallow bathymetric ridges. This has significant implications because grounded icebergs anchor sea ice, with thicker sea ice often fastened to them. Such fast ice favours the opening of coastal polynyas, where most of the Antarctic sea ice is produced. Simulating their presence and extensions properly in ocean models would improve our ability to project future sea-ice production rates and water mass transformation, including Antarctic Bottom Water formation.

In OCEAN ICE's WP2, we have developed a new generation of Lagrangian iceberg model that are capable of interacting with bathymetry. First, this has required some work to better estimate the thickness of icebergs (section 2.2.1). Indeed, most modelling studies used a thickness of 250 m for the largest iceberg classes, following the typical ice-shelf thickness suggested by ship observations, and independently of the calving location. In reality, icebergs inherit the thickness of their calving ice shelf, and their keel depth often exceeds 400 m, making them more likely to ground on bathymetric ridges. The second part of our work has consisted of explicitly representing the dissipative forces at the iceberg base when they move over shallow bathymetry, and the upward motion of icebergs during the grounding process, when a part of their kinetic energy is transformed into potential energy (section 2.2.2).

2.2 Description of the work performed

The two following subsections make use of the NEMO ocean–sea-ice–iceberg model (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean; Madec and the NEMO System Team, 2024). Lagrangian icebergs were introduced in NEMO by Marsh et al. (2015) and later improved by Merino et al. (2016) to use 3-dimensional ocean temperatures and velocities to calculate the melt rates and acceleration of icebergs. All this work has been designed as a collaboration between CNRS-IGE and UKRI-BAS, and the results have been discussed in monthly online meetings. The work presented in section 2.2.1 was led by A. Olivé Abelló, N. Jourdain and P. Mathiot at CNRS-IGE. The work presented in section 2.2.2. was led by Y. Kostov and P. Holland at UKRI-BAS.

2.2.1 More realistic thickness of simulated icebergs to enable their grounding

We have revised the iceberg thickness distribution in 0.25° simulations of the Southern Ocean by imposing that the largest icebergs have the thickness of the ice shelf from which they calve. Using observational ice shelf thicknesses results in icebergs with a broader thickness distribution and keels that can exceed 600 m. We have then implemented an extremely simple scheme to represent the icebergs interaction with

bathymetry: if an iceberg moves to an ocean grid cell where the sea floor is shallower than its keel, then it is moved back to its previous floating position and its velocity is set to zero. As a result, the simulated icebergs interact with 31% of the bathymetric features of the Antarctic continental shelf that are shallower than 400 m, particularly in front of the Ronne-Filchner and Thwaites ice shelves. The estimated iceberg grounding probability reasonably reproduces satellite observations over the shallow ridges of the Amundsen Sea (Fig. 1) and is consistent with the observed fast ice distribution elsewhere.

Fig. 1: Probability of (a) iceberg occurrence from Mazur et al. (2017) inferred from SAR images, and (b) grounded icebergs in the simulation, including a simple grounding scheme, in the Amundsen Sea. The grey solid lines indicate the bathymetry contours, and the light blue shading represents the Antarctic ice shelves.

Iceberg melting over the Antarctic continental shelf reaches an average of 630 Gt yr^{-1} if icebergs do not interact with bathymetry, and of 800 Gt yr^{-1} if a simple grounding scheme is used. This is probably a low-end

estimation of this effect because this simple grounding scheme does not represent the residence time of icebergs on their grounding site. Pine Island –Thwaites and Ross West are the basins contributing the most to this change, increasing by 12 and 17 Gt yr⁻¹, respectively, when icebergs interact with bathymetry. Such additional freshwater injected in an area prone to sea ice production has important consequences for the ocean properties around Antarctica. This freshwater enhances the ocean stratification, limiting deep convection and favouring the intrusion of relatively warm CDW onto some parts of the continental shelf. This effect is particularly pronounced in the Amundsen Sea, where the bottom temperatures and salinities increase by more than 0.2°C and 0.02 g kg⁻¹, respectively.

More importantly, grounded icebergs also block drifting sea ice and favour areas of thick sea ice when a fast-ice parametrization is included. Even though further work is needed to fully model complex sea-ice–iceberg and bathymetry–iceberg interactions, the iceberg module in NEMO can already simulate fast ice blocked by icebergs in regions where high sea-ice persistence is observed in satellite products.

As for grounding, a lot of work would be needed to accurately represent the iceberg–sea-ice interactions for simulating thicker sea-ice cover fastened to grounded icebergs. We have conducted experiments in which we represent these interactions in simple ways. The first approach makes use of the iceberg–fast-ice parameterization of Lemieux et al. (2015, 2016): sea ice over a grid cell where at least one iceberg has grounded once feels an additional basal stress term to the sea-ice momentum equation and a tensile strength to account for sea-ice arch formation. The second approach consists of treating grid cells in which at least one iceberg has grounded as land cells blocking ocean and sea-ice advection in NEMO. For both approaches, we obtain similar sea-ice thickness distribution; thicker sea ice accumulates on the eastern side (“upstream”) of grounded icebergs, while thinner sea ice is found on the western side (“downstream”) where coastal polynyas are expected (Fig. 2). Sea ice is thickened by more than 2 m in front of Thwaites Glacier, the Ronne-Filchner Ice Shelf, the western Ross Sea, and in East Antarctica. In contrast, implementing iceberg grounding without interaction with sea ice does not significantly impact the sea ice thickness, only in the northern part of the Antarctic Peninsula (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Probability of grounded icebergs (25-year climatology) together with the distribution of fast ice persistence calculated from contiguous maps of the NASA Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (Fraser et al., 2021) for the 2000-2018 period and expressed as a percentage of time covering each pixel. Bathymetry contours, from 1000 to 4000 m, are represented as solid grey lines.

Our simple “grounding” method is useful to investigate the effects of the presence of thick icebergs in the Southern Ocean. It is nonetheless unable to represent the residence time of grounded icebergs on the bathymetric ridges, which is treated in the following subsection.

2.2.2 Dynamics of iceberg grounding and ungrounding

This work focuses on the Amundsen Sea, Antarctica, and more specifically on Bear Ridge where numerous icebergs are observed to ground and unground (near 110°W in Fig. 1). The physics discussed in this section and the implementation in NEMO should nonetheless be of interest for the entire Southern Ocean.

As they drift, icebergs may run into bathymetric obstacles or plough into seafloor sediment. Iceberg scours (also called ploughmarks) are widespread on the seafloor in the Amundsen Sea. In OCEAN ICE, we have manually mapped more than 60 scours from existing multibeam-bathymetric data on the eastern flank and central part of Bear Ridge as a representative population of modern scours. We have described their morphology to characterise modern iceberg grounding events, and to calibrate the modelled scouring.

To assess the influence of sediment resistance on iceberg grounding, we have compiled wet bulk density (WBD) and shear strength data for representative sediment cores recovered from the Amundsen Sea (Smith et al., 2011; Clark et al., 2024). The composition of seafloor sediments in the Amundsen Sea typically consists of three broad lithological units, from soft, water-rich muds of low shear strength and density, to stiff compacted till, with a transitional layer of coarse-grained stratified to structureless, sandy to gravelly, terrigenous sediments in between. These sedimentary strata overlie a solid crystalline basement and/or lithified sedimentary strata that cannot be penetrated by iceberg ploughing.

Based on these data, we have assumed the existence of a uniform 8-m sediment layer with submerged unit weight of 8 kN m^{-3} and shear resistance of 6 kPa. Beneath this single uniform sediment layer, we assume the existence of a basement. Thus, iceberg ploughing is allowed to occur up to a maximum of 8-m depth while it remains in motion, but then other forces come into play, described next. When a moving grounded iceberg ploughs through all the sediment and reaches a sloping basement, it can move up the basement slope if the berg has enough momentum and/or sufficient sources of sustained acceleration (Chari 1975). As the berg moves up the slope, it is lifted upwards, its freeboard increases, and as a result, the buoyancy force of the ocean no longer balances the weight of the iceberg and a force directed into the basement supports the remainder (Fig. 3). This gives rise to a gravitational force, which converts the kinetic energy of the iceberg motion into potential energy upon grounding, and also causes a solid body friction between the berg and the basement, which can be represented as a Coulomb sliding law by analogy to the basal friction of glaciers.

Fig. 3: Vertical force budget. An idealized schematic of an iceberg trajectory (green arrow) going up a topographic slope. The angle of the trajectory (solid green arrow) relative to its projection on the horizontal x-y plane (dashed grey arrow) is denoted. The local maximum slope of the topography is denoted β . The vector normal to the topography is indicated with a brown line. Schematic angles not shown to scale with respect to the relevant topographic slopes.

We have implemented the relevant iceberg dynamics and grounding theory as an update to the existing representation of Lagrangian icebergs in NEMO, and we have tested the modified model in the 0.25° Amundsen Sea configuration described in Caillet et al. (2023). Iceberg motion is computed using a separate numerical scheme within NEMO, which enables temporal sub-stepping within the iceberg code, while keeping the same time step for the ocean and sea-ice. We found that allowing a shorter iceberg timestep is numerically important when modelling the shape and evolution of iceberg scours because forces such as gravity along the sloping topography may act on much shorter timescales compared to other sources of acceleration. To test our new implementations, we release 497 identical tabular icebergs in the region east of Bear Ridge enclosed by 109.9°W, 106.2°W, 74.3°S, and 72.0°S, all of them having the same mass of $3.9 \cdot 10^{11}$ kg, a uniform density of 875 kg/m^3 , and a thickness of 395 m.

We first analyse the force balance of freely floating icebergs (Fig. 4). The atmospheric drag, the ocean pressure gradients, and the Coriolis force are the dominant forces and are nearly in a three-way balance with very little net acceleration. The Coriolis force is oriented solely to the left, perpendicular to the direction of iceberg motion, while the wind stress and ocean pressure gradient force are mostly oriented to the right of the direction of motion. The corresponding forces that are nearly orthogonal to the direction of motion do very little work on the freely floating large icebergs. Episodes of particularly strong winds drive icebergs somewhat more efficiently than they accelerate the surrounding water column. In such cases, the ocean exerts a small but noticeable drag that decelerates icebergs

We then analyse the force balance of grounding icebergs, i.e., icebergs that are ploughing the sediment layer but still moving (Fig. 5). The force due to ocean drag is much weaker than the pressure gradient force and the Coriolis force. In contrast to the case of floating icebergs, the ocean drag does not exhibit a clear prevailing orientation against the direction of motion, and the ocean pressure gradients are not purely orthogonal to the iceberg trajectories. Instead of pointing mostly to the right, as is the case for freely-floating icebergs, the pressure gradient force on kinetically grounded icebergs can point in any of multiple directions. The difference in the relative orientation of the sea-ice drag is noticeable as well: when the icebergs are grounded, sea-ice drag acts to push them forward rather than decelerate them or act in a direction orthogonal to their trajectory. Even more importantly, grounding icebergs experience a large forward push by atmospheric drag and an even larger net deceleration force due to the sediment resistance. The latter means that these icebergs moving along the bottom topography are rarely in force balance. When icebergs plough all the way to the basement, they experience Coulomb friction that compensate the down-slope gravitational acceleration due to their position on the bedrock, above floatation (not shown). These additional forces bring icebergs to rest within a day of contact with the basement, and the icebergs are no longer kinetically grounded.

Fig. 4: Contributions of (a) atmospheric drag, (b) oceanic pressure gradients, (c) Coriolis force, (d) ocean drag, and (e) sea-ice drag to the net acceleration (f) of simulated freely floating icebergs of 395 m thickness in the Amundsen Sea simulations. Directions are denoted as F (forward, along the iceberg’s direction of motion), B (backward), L (to the left), R (to the right). The size of radial bars indicates the probability density function of the acceleration direction for a given component (in each panel, the sum of all directions is 100%, but acceleration along some of the directions is on smaller orders of magnitude). For a given bar, the probability of several acceleration ranges is indicated by the colours (probability related to the radial distance).

Fig. 5: Same as Fig. 4, but for iceberg grounding (i.e., ploughing the sediment layer but still moving) on Bear Ridge, Amundsen Sea.

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2.4 Open Science

Peer-reviewed publications

Two publications in open access are now available:

- Olivé Abelló A., Mathiot P., Jourdain N. C., Kostov Y., Holland P. R., Rousset, C. and Gascouin, S. (2025), The grounding of thick icebergs enhances the freshwater release on the Antarctic continental shelf, *JGR Oceans*, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2025JC022857>, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* Volume 130, Issue 10 e2025JC022857

- Kostov, Y., Holland, P. R., Hogan, K. A., Smith, J. A., Jourdain, N. C., Mathiot, P., Olivé Abelló, A., Fleming, A. H., and Meijers, A. J. S.: Modelled dynamics of floating and grounded icebergs, with application to the Amundsen Sea, *The Cryosphere*, 20, 135–169, <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-20-135-2026>, 2026.

Model developments

Our modifications of the NEMO iceberg module aim to be integrated into an official release of NEMO-5. This will be achieved through the land-ice Working group and the Developers Committee of NEMO, both led by Pierre Mathiot. The NEMO code is public, developed under the CECILL license, which is a French adaptation of the GNU GPL (General Public License).

3. Results

We have produced a novel algorithm that simulates iceberg grounding and consists of (1) a scheme to calculate the iceberg thickness inherited from their calving site depending on their size, and (2) a scheme to calculate the forces driving the iceberg motion when is in contact with the sediments or the solid bedrock. We have the provided proofs of feasibility for these schemes by using them in realistic simulations of the entire Southern Ocean or the Amundsen Sea.

Through this work in OCEAN ICE, two early career researchers have gained experience on this emerging field of research. We have also initiated a network of researchers working on iceberg grounding and fast ice in Antarctica, involving the authors of this deliverable, as well as researchers from the Institute Pierre Simon Laplace (IPSL, France), the Catholic University of Louvain (UCL, Belgium), and the Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies (IMAS, Australia).

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action:

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models, using historical observations and new data sets obtained in the project.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by representing a new process (iceberg grounding) in the NEMO ocean model, using remote sensing observations of grounded icebergs as well as field observations of scours left by icebergs in the sediments.

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by improving the realism of freshwater fluxes in the Southern Ocean.